

Synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes with 5-methyl-1-(2'-pyridyl)pyrazole-3-carboxylic acid and 5-methyl-1-(4',6'-dimethyl-2'-pyrimidyl)pyrazole-3-carboxylic acid

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Abstract : Synthesis and characterization of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes with title ligands, 1 and 2 (abbreviated as PyPzCH and PymPzCH respectively) were carried out by elemental analyses, mass, IR and PMR spectral studies. Magnetic and electronic spectral features classify the reported bis-chelates as six coordinated distorted octahedral ones. A comparative study of IR spectra between the ligands and the complexes indicate different denticity of the ligands. The neutral bidentate ligand 1 functions through pyrazolyl 2_N and pyridyl 1'_N (tertiary N atoms) and the ligand 2, in its zwitter ion form (achieved during complexation) exercises tridentate behaviour through pyrazolyl 2_N, pyrimidyl 1'_N (tertiary N atoms) and carboxylic acid oxygen. Hence, the different coordination environments viz. MN₄X₂ (M = Ni^{II}/Cu^{II}) for ligand 1 and MN₄O₂ (M = Co^{II}/Ni^{II}/Cu^{II}) for ligand 2 are indicated. Electrochemical studies of some of the Cu^{II} species demonstrate easy oxidative nature of Cu^{II}.

Keywords : Cobalt(II) complex, nickel(II) complex, copper(II) complex, synthesis, spectroscopy.

In continuation of our earlier reports¹ on the synthesis and characterisation of the transition metal ion complexes with diazole- and diazine-derived ligands, the present communication reports the coordination behaviour of two substituted pyrazole-carboxylic acids (1 and 2) with additional donor site(s) at 1-position of the pyrazole-moiety. The metal ions are cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II).

Results and discussion

The mass spectra of the two title ligands give molecular ion peaks at *m/z* 203 for 1 and 232 for 2 in agreement

with their empirical formulae C₁₀H₉N₃O₂ and C₁₁H₁₂N₄O₂ respectively. The IR spectra of the ligands show strong bands appearing at 1700 for 1 and 1710 cm⁻¹ for 2 attributable to the asymmetric stretches of OCO⁻ and the corresponding symmetric stretching modes appear at 1425 and 1430 cm⁻¹ respectively. The ν_{C-N} modes of vibrations of pyridine/pyrimidine and pyrazole appear at 1595 and 1470 cm⁻¹ for 1 and those for 2 appear at 1590 and 1535 cm⁻¹. The pK_a values of 1 and 2 are found to be 4.03 and 3.63 respectively.

Cobalt(II) complexes of PymPzCH, conform to the general composition [Co(HPymPzC)₂]X₂.nH₂O as ascertained from analytical data (Table 1); the RT (30 °C) magnetic moment values (4.72–5.21 B.M.) (Table 1) are indicative of high spin octahedral cobalt(II) complexes². The molar conductance (Λ_M) values (Table 1) recorded in dry methanol (Λ_M = 140–200 mho cm² mol⁻¹) are indicative of 1 : 2 electrolytic nature³ at least in solution of the said solvent. The diffuse reflectance spectra (d.r.s.) of the present Co^{II} species indicate an overall octahedral environment in the region 7420–8645 and 17825–20410

[†]Deceased.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of cobalt, nickel and copper complexes

Sl. no.	Complex (Colour)	Elemental analysis(%) : Found/(Calcd.)					Λ_M^b	μ_{eff} at 30 °C (B.M.)
		C	H	N	Metal	Anion		
1.	[Co(HPyPzC) ₂]Cl ₂ (Bright pink)	44.7 (44.4)	3.9 (4.0)	18.5 (18.9)	9.7 (9.9)	12.2 (11.9)	200	5.21
2.	[Co(HPyPzC) ₂]Br ₂ .2H ₂ O (Bluish grey)	36.8 (36.7)	3.8 (3.9)	15.6 (15.1)	8.2 (8.2)	22.4 (22.2)	160	5.16
3.	[Co(HPyPzC) ₂]I ₂ (Yellowish green)	34.1 (34.0)	3.2 (3.0)	14.2 (14.4)	7.7 (7.6)	32.8 (32.0)	140	4.88
4.	[Co(HPyPzC) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (Pink)	40.6 (40.8)	3.8 (3.7)	21.4 (21.6) ^a	9.2 (9.1)	-	190	4.82
5.	[Co(HPyPzC) ₂]SO ₄ .2H ₂ O (Pink)	40.6 (40.3)	4.4 (4.3)	16.9 (17.1)	8.9 (9.0)	-	80	4.54
6.	[Co(HPyPzC) ₂](BF ₄) ₂ (Pink)	38.1 (37.9)	3.5 (3.4)	15.8 (16.0)	8.8 (8.5)	-	150	4.66
7.	[Co(HPyPzC) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂ .2H ₂ O (Pink)	35.0 (34.8)	3.7 (3.7)	14.5 (14.8)	7.9 (7.8)	-	160	4.72
8.	[Ni(PyPzCH) ₂]Cl ₂ .4H ₂ O (Deep green)	39.6 (39.5)	4.4 (4.3)	13.6 (13.8)	9.6 (9.7)	11.9 (11.5)	140	2.95
9.	[Ni(PyPzCH) ₂]Br ₂ .2H ₂ O (Green)	36.5 (36.3)	3.4 (3.3)	12.4 (12.7)	8.9 (8.9)	24.4 (24.2)	180	3.10
10.	[Ni(PyPzCH) ₂]I ₂ (Yellowish grey)	33.5 (33.4)	2.6 (2.5)	11.5 (11.7)	8.0 (8.2)	35.7 (35.3)	140	3.06
11.	[Ni(PyPzCH) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ .2H ₂ O (Light green)	38.6 (38.4)	3.6 (3.5)	17.7 ^a (17.9)	9.4 (9.4)	-	130	2.86
12.	[Ni(PyPzCH) ₂](SCN) ₂ (Blue-violet)	45.7 (45.5)	3.1 (3.1)	19.1 ^a (19.3)	10.0 (10.1)	-	150	2.98
13.	[Ni(PyPzCH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].(BF ₄) ₂ (Blue-violet)	35.4 (35.6)	3.4 (3.3)	12.2 (12.6)	8.9 (8.7)	-	140	3.12
14.	[Ni(PyPzCH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].(ClO ₄) ₂ (Deep green)	34.4 (34.3)	3.2 (3.1)	11.9 (12.0)	8.5 (8.4)	-	160	3.02
15.	[Ni(HPyPzC) ₂]Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O (Light green)	42.1 (42.9)	4.6 (4.4)	17.7 (17.8)	9.1 (9.3)	11.4 (11.3)	190	3.21
16.	[Ni(HPyPzC) ₂]Br ₂ (Green)	38.9 (38.7)	3.5 (3.5)	16.1 (16.4)	8.5 (8.6)	23.5 (23.4)	210	2.98
17.	[Ni(HPyPzC) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ .2H ₂ O (Bright green)	40.6 (40.8)	3.9 (3.7)	21.3 ^a (21.6)	9.1 (9.0)	-	160	3.29
18.	[Ni(HPyPzC) ₂]SO ₄ .2H ₂ O (Green)	40.7 (40.3)	4.1 (4.3)	16.7 (17.1)	9.2 (9.0)	-	110	3.13
19.	[Ni(HPyPzC) ₂](BF ₄) ₂ .2H ₂ O (Deep green)	36.0 (36.0)	4.0 (3.8)	15.1 (15.3)	8.2 (8.0)	-	210	3.38
20.	[Ni(HPyPzC) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂ .2H ₂ O (Green)	36.7 (36.6)	3.1 (3.3)	15.6 (15.5)	8.3 (8.1)	-	190	2.90
21.	[Cu(PyPzCH) ₂]Cl ₂ (Bright green)	44.7 (44.4)	3.4 (3.3)	15.3 (15.5)	11.5 (11.8)	13.4 (13.1)	130	2.2
22.	[Cu(PyPzCH) ₂]Br ₂ (Dark green)	38.0 (38.1)	2.9 (2.9)	13.2 (13.3)	10.2 (10.0)	25.6 (25.4)	140	1.70

Table-1 (contd.)

23.	[Cu(PyPzCH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂] (Blue)	40.5 (40.4)	2.9 (3.0)	18.8 ^a (18.9)	10.5 (10.7)	-	130	1.87
24.	[Cu(PyPzCH) ₂ (SCN) ₂] (Yellowish green)	45.3 (45.1)	3.2 (3.1)	19.0 ^a (19.1)	10.5 (10.9)	-	160	2.18
25.	[Cu(PyPzCH) ₂ (BF ₄) ₂].2H ₂ O (Green)	35.6 (35.3)	3.3 (3.2)	12.1 (12.4)	9.2 (9.3)	-	120	2.20
26.	[Cu(PyPzCH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].(ClO ₄) ₂ (Green)	34.4 (34.1)	3.0 (3.1)	11.8 (11.9)	9.1 (9.0)	-	150	2.04
27.	[Cu(HPymPzC) ₂ Cl ₂].2H ₂ O (Light green)	41.8 (41.6)	4.5 (4.4)	17.6 (17.7)	9.8 (10.0)	11.3 (11.1)	200	1.92
28.	[Cu(HPymPzC) ₂]Br ₂ (Yellowish green)	38.5 (38.4)	3.3 (3.5)	16.0 (16.3)	9.1 (9.2)	23.0 (23.3)	140	2.01
29.	[Cu(HPymPzC) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ .2H ₂ O (Bluish green)	38.4 (38.4)	4.1 (4.1)	20.0 ^a (20.3)	9.0 (9.2)	-	140	1.68
30.	[Cu(HPymPzC) ₂]SO ₄ .2H ₂ O (Light green)	40.4 (40.0)	4.3 (4.2)	16.8 (17.0)	9.4 (9.6)	-	90	1.74
31.	[Cu(HPymPzC) ₂](BF ₄) ₂ .2H ₂ O (Deep green)	36.9 (36.6)	3.7 (3.7)	14.5 (14.7)	8.4 (8.3)	-	150	2.13
32.	[Cu(HPymPzC) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂ .2H ₂ O (Yellowish green)	37.9 (37.6)	3.5 (3.4)	15.6 (16.0)	8.7 (9.1)	-	170	1.87

^aIncluding nitrogen present in the anions; ^bconductivity in MeOH (mho cm² mol⁻¹).

cm⁻¹ which may be assigned as ν_1 [${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$] and ν_3 [${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$] transitions⁴ respectively. Using the two known relationships⁵, it has been possible to deduce the ligand field parameters ($Dq = 845\text{--}935$, $B = 702\text{--}891$ cm⁻¹ and $\beta = 0.72\text{--}0.93$) from the assigned positions of ν_1 and ν_3 bands; these are quite consistent with those reported earlier⁵ for octahedral cobalt(II) species. Using the relationship $\nu_2 = \nu_1 + 10Dq$, the position of ν_2 bands are found to lie in the region 16000–18000 cm⁻¹, very close to ν_3 bands as expected. The solution spectra of these species indicate no significant change in geometry on dissolution. Nickel(II) complexes conform to the general composition [Ni(PyPzCH)₂X₂].nH₂O ($X = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , SCN^-), [Ni(PyPzCH)₂(H₂O)₂]X₂ ($X = \text{ClO}_4^-$, BF_4^-) and [Ni(HPymPzC)₂]X₂.nH₂O as ascertained from analytical data (Table 1); the effective magnetic moment values (μ_{eff}) (Table 1) of the species fall in the range 2.86–3.38 B.M. at RT (30 °C) expected for 6-coordinate nickel(II) complexes⁶. The methanolic solutions of these Ni^{II} species furnish molar conductances ($\Lambda_M = 130\text{--}210$ mho cm² mol⁻¹) are indicative of 1 : 2 electrolytic nature³ (for sulphate species, $\Lambda_M = 110$ mho cm² mol⁻¹ indicating 1 : 1 electrolyte³) at least in solution of the said solvent. The d.r.s. of the reported bis-chelate of Ni^{II} consist of

three main bands appearing in the region 8620–10440, 14450–19100 and 23800–26955 cm⁻¹ which can be safely assigned to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) respectively in an O_h symmetry. An additional band appearing around 30000 cm⁻¹ could be due to LMCT transitions. The ligand field parameters ($Dq = 860\text{--}1045$ cm⁻¹, $B = 810\text{--}1035$ cm⁻¹, $\beta = 0.73\text{--}0.95$ and $\nu_2/\nu_1 = 1.60\text{--}1.98$) substantiate an overall octahedral geometry^{5,6}. All the present bis-chelates of Ni^{II} on dissolution in methanol show electronic spectra suggesting no gross departure in geometry in an innocent solvent. The copper(II) complexes conform to the composition [Cu(PyPzCH)₂X₂].nH₂O, [Cu(PyPzCH)₂(H₂O)₂](ClO₄)₂ and [Cu(HPymPzC)₂]X₂.nH₂O as ascertained from analytical data (Table 1); the RT (30 °C) magnetic moment values (μ_{eff}) in the range 1.68–2.21 B.M. (Table 1) furnish no major interactions between the two Cu^{II} ions⁷ [with the exception that the nitrate species of PymPzCH ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.68$ B.M.) may contain some interactions between Cu^{II} ions]. The methanolic solutions of this species furnish molar conductance (Table 1) which are indicative 1 : 2 electrolytic in nature except 1 : 1 for sulphate species. The reflectance spectra of the present Cu^{II} complexes exhibit a strong broad band in the region 12000–14370 cm⁻¹; the nature

of the curve in such case; clearly indicate that more than one transitions are buried under the absorption envelope. Studies^{4,8,9} on the electronic spectra of Cu^{II} complexes have indicated that the three transitions ${}^2B_1 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ (ν_1), ${}^2B_1 \rightarrow {}^2B_2$ (ν_2) and ${}^2B_1 \rightarrow {}^2E$ (ν_3) are close in energy often giving rise to a single broad band envelope. Thus, the present Cu^{II} species are best regarded as having distorted octahedral structures with a symmetry lower than O_h , though the extent of distortion is not known. An additional band in all these cases appearing in the region 22940–27470 cm^{-1} could be due LMCT transition. However, electronic spectral data in methanol indicate that there is no stereochemical change on dissolution.

Infrared spectra of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes reveal that the asymmetric OCO^- stretching frequency in the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} species of PyPzCH , suffers +ve shift ($\Delta\nu = 10\text{--}30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) while the symmetric OCO^- suffers slight +ve or -ve shift; these observations substantiate the non-participation¹⁰ of $-\text{COOH}$ group in coordination. However, the asymmetric stretches of OCO^- in the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} species of PymPzCH reflect -ve shift ($\Delta\nu = 50\text{--}110 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) while the symmetric stretches of OCO^- suffer slightly +ve or -ve shift; the observations substantiate the participation¹¹ of $-\text{COOH}$ group through uninegative oxygen in all the species of PymPzCH . In all the bis-chelates of PymPzCH , an additional band in the region 3120–3140 cm^{-1} could be attributed to $\nu_{\text{N-H}}^{\text{sym}}$ vibration¹² of the zwitter ion form $[\text{HPymPzC}]$ and the same is achieved during complexation at the pH $\sim 5\text{--}6$. The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (pyrazole) in all the species of PyPzCH and PymPzCH suffers a +ve shift ($\Delta\nu = 5\text{--}45 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), $\nu_{\text{N=N}}$ (pyrazole) attains +ve shift ($\Delta\nu = 10\text{--}30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (pyridine/pyrimidine) also gains +ve shift ($\Delta\nu = 5\text{--}30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$); these observations clearly indicate that the tertiary N atoms i.e. pyrazolyl 2_{N} and pyridyl/pyrimidyl $1'_{\text{N}}$ are the points of attachment^{13,14} to the central metal ions respectively. The presence of H_2O molecule (lattice) in the hydrated complexes has been indicated by the broad bands in the region 3500–3200 cm^{-1} which may be attributed¹⁵ due to the O–H stretching mode of attached water molecule. In addition appearance of frequencies $\sim 820\text{--}800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the perchlorate species of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} and fluoborate species of Ni^{II} with PyPzCH could be associated with $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ of coordinated H_2O molecule¹⁵. The far IR data for the metal ion complexes show non-ligand bands which can be safely assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ (420–480 cm^{-1} ; uninegative O of $-\text{COOH}$ of PymPzCH in its zwitter ion form)¹⁶, $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ (260–340 cm^{-1} ; pyrazolyl 2_{N})¹⁷, $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ (250–270 cm^{-1} ; pyridyl/pyrimidyl $1'_{\text{N}}$)^{18–20}. The mode of attachment of the anions (X) [$\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , SCN^- , ClO_4^- , BF_4^- , $\frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4^{2-}$] in the reported metal ion species can be qualitatively inferred from the IR data as follows: (i) when the ligand is PyPzCH : (a) the halo complexes show metal-halogen stretching frequencies around 300–320 cm^{-1} [differentiable from $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ (ring)] which may be attributed to M–X stretches²¹, (b) nitrate species exhibit three bands of which two (1300–1380 cm^{-1}) could be components of ν_3 and the third ($\sim 800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) be the ν_2 vibration of a monodentate nitrate group in C_{2v} symmetry^{12,22}, (c) thiocyanate species contain bands around 2100 and 800 cm^{-1} which could be assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ ^{12,23} vibration and $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ stretch of N-bonded²⁴ NCS, (d) fluoborate complex of Cu^{II} exhibits bands around ~ 1160 , ~ 1070 and $\sim 1040 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which support the presence of a monodentate BF_4 in C_{3v} symmetry²⁵ and the same in Ni^{II} contains a broad band around 1080–1030 cm^{-1} attributable to ν_3 mode of ionic BF_4 in T_d symmetry^{26,27} and (e) perchlorate species of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} reflect broad bands around 1120–1090 and 1160–1080 cm^{-1} with another strong band $\sim 620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicate the presence of ionic ClO_4 group in T_d symmetry²⁸. (ii) when the ligand is PymPzCH : (a) nitrate species exhibit two broad bands around 1380–1310 cm^{-1} and $\sim 800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively which can be due to the ν_3 and ν_2 modes of ionic NO_3 in D_{3h} symmetry^{12,29}, (b) the appearance of strong broad band around 1190–1040 cm^{-1} of the sulphate species indicates T_d symmetry is not lowered and hence SO_4 ion is not coordinate¹², (c) the presence of a strong but very sharp band covering 1120–1020 cm^{-1} in the fluoborate species indicates the ionic nature of BF_4 and the said band may arise from ν_3 mode of BF_4 in T_d symmetry^{12,22} and (d) perchlorate species containing a very strong band around 1160–1050 cm^{-1} and a sharp band around 625 cm^{-1} indicate the original T_d symmetry of ClO_4 ion and hence ClO_4 is not coordinated²⁸. Thus in the light of the discussion from IR data (4000–200 cm^{-1}) it appears that the central metal ions has an overall octahedral geometry. The ligand, PyPzCH , in the bis-chelates of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} exercises a neutral bidentate (NN) through pyrazolyl 2_{N} and pyridyl $1'_{\text{N}}$ respectively, the carboxylic acid group remains non-participating in the chelates. Fate of the majority of the anions (X) is coordinated (with the exception ClO_4 in both Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} and BF_4 in Ni^{II} species are ionic). On the other hand, the ligand, PymPzCH in its zwitter ion form (HPymPzC) (achieved during complexation around pH $\sim 5\text{--}6$) exercises tridentate behaviour (NNO) through pyrazolyl 2_{N} , pyrimidyl $1'_{\text{N}}$ and uninegative carboxylic acid oxygen. The counter ions retain their ionic character.

ESR spectra of copper(II) complexes at RT (~30 °C) :

The ESR spectra of the chloride and bromide species of PymPzCH exhibit a one-g value spectra indicative of isotropic behaviour of dynamic or pseudo-rotational type of Jahn-Teller distortion³⁰ and the observations lead to distorted octahedral geometry. The ESR spectra of chloro- and bromo-species of PyPzCH and nitrate and sulphate-species of PymPzCH in polycrystalline form exhibit no hyperfine structure and they show similar anisotropic feature with $g_{||} > g_{\perp} > 2$ (Table 2). The nitrate species of PyPzCH furnishes three-g value spectrum for which again $g_{||} > g_{\perp} > 2$. In all the cases it is found that $g_{av} > 2.00$. These observations clearly indicate a tetragonal distorted geometry^{25,31} associated with $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state. The chloro-species of PyPzCH with $G > 4$ reflects that exchange coupling⁵ is negligible in it. All the other species with $G < 4.0$ (Table 2) have some exchange interactions.

Electrochemistry of some Cu^{II} species viz. chloro- and fluoroborate-species of PyPzCH and chloro- and nitrate species of PymPzCH in dry MeOH in the potential range +1.20 to -1.20 V vs SCE provides that in each case, Cu^{II} gets reduced to Cu^I irreversibly around -0.30 V vs SCE. The well-defined redox couple formed in the +ve potential area is due to Cu^{III}/Cu^{II} system³³; the anodic peak potential corresponds to the oxidation of Cu^{II} ($3d^9$) to Cu^{III} ($3d^8$) and the cathodic counterpart is due to quasi-reversible one-electron change process, since the ratio I_p^{red}/I_p^{ox} is very close to one and is expressed as Cu^{II} \rightleftharpoons Cu^{III} + e. The $E_{1/2}$ values are dependent on the nature of the coordinated ions. The smaller $E_{1/2}$ value of the fluoroborate-species of PyPzCH indicates easier oxidation of Cu^{II} ions and this can be explained due to the higher electron withdrawing power of BF₄ (coordinated) than coordinated chloride ion (ligand is PyPzCH), which facilitate the oxidation. The $E_{1/2}$ value of the two species of PymPzCH are found to be nearly equal and hence it is

inferred that the environment around the central metal ion (CuN₄O₂) are same which is further supporting the earlier propositions made from IR data. The metallic copper deposited in the electrode surface gets irreversibly oxidised in the potential range -0.08 to +0.08 V vs SCE in each run.

Experimental

All the materials used for the preparation of the ligands and complexes were AnalaR grade quality and were used without further purification. Spectrograde solvents were used for spectral, conductance and electrochemical measurements. DMSO-*d*₆ (Aldrich) was used for recording ¹H NMR data.

Synthesis of ligands : The ligand, 5-methyl-1-(2'-pyridyl)pyrazole-3-carboxylic acid (PyPzCH) was prepared by the condensation of sodium salt of ethylacetopyruvate and 2-pyridyl hydrazine by following a known method³⁴. The product on recrystallisation from ethanol melted at 192 °C (Found : C, 59.3; H, 4.3; N, 20.7. Calcd. for C₁₀H₉N₃O₂ : C, 59.1; H, 4.4; N, 20.7%). The ligand 5-methyl-1-(4',6'-dimethyl-2'-pyrimidyl)pyrazole-3-carboxylic acid (PymPzCH) was prepared by the condensation of sodium salt of ethyl-acetopyruvate and 2-hydrazino-4,6-dimethyl pyrimidine by following a known method³⁴. The product on recrystallisation from ethanol melted at 148 °C (Found : C, 57.2; H, 5.1; N, 23.9. Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₂N₄O₂ : C, 56.9; H, 5.2; N, 24.1%).

Synthesis of metal ion complexes of PyPzCH : $[M(PyPzCH)_2X_2].nH_2O$ ($M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}; X = Cl^-, Br^-, I^-, NO_3^-, SCN^-$ and $X = BF_4^-$ when $M = Cu^{II}; n = 0, 2, 4$), $[Ni(PyPzCH)_2(H_2O)_2]X_2$ ($X = ClO_4^-, BF_4^-$) and $[Cu(PyPzCH)_2(H_2O)_2](ClO_4)_2$:

An ethanolic solution of MX₂.nH₂O (0.0015 mol) was added to a solution of the ligand (0.061 g, 0.003 mol) in the same solvent. The resultant solution (pH ~3-4) was

Table 2. ESR spectral parameters of some of the representative Cu^{II} complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	$g_{ }$	g_{\perp}	g_{iso}	g_{av}	G
1.	[Cu(PyPzCH) ₂ Cl ₂]	2.28	2.04	-	2.12	7.0
2.	[Cu(PyPzCH) ₂ Br ₂]	2.22	2.07	-	2.12	3.13
3.	[Cu(PyPzCH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	2.26	2.08	-	2.14	3.25
			2.11 / 2.05			
4.	[Cu(HPymPzC ₂) ₂]Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	-	-	2.14	-	-
5.	[Cu(HPymPzC ₂) ₂]Br ₂	-	-	2.16	-	-
6.	[Cu(HPymPzC ₂) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ .2H ₂ O	2.23	2.13	-	2.16	1.78
7.	[Cu(HPymPzC ₂) ₂]SO ₄ .2H ₂ O	2.29	2.18	-	2.22	1.61

concentrated on a water bath and on cooling microcrystalline compounds separated out in each case. The compounds were filtered off, washed with cold ethanol and dried over silica gel.

Synthesis of metal ion complexes of PymPzCH : $[M(\text{HPymPzC})_2]X_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (HPymPzC = zwitter ion form of PymPzCH achieved during complexation; $M = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$, Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} ; $X = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , $\frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4^{2-}$, BF_4^- , ClO_4^- ; $n = 0, 2$) :

An ethanolic solution of $\text{MX}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.001 mol) (aqueous alcoholic when $X = \frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4$) was added to a solution of the ligand (0.46 g, 0.002 mol) (pH found to be ~3-4). Dilute ammonia solution addition raised the pH ~5-6 and the resultant solution was concentrated on a water bath. After cooling to addition of 10 ml acetone yielded the microcrystalline compounds in each case. It was filtered, washed and dried in a desiccator.

Physical measurements : C, H and N analyses were carried out with a Perkin-Elmer CHNS/O analyser 2400 at IACS (Kolkata). Mass spectrum of the ligand was recorded at RSIC, Chennai, with Finnigan Mat 8230 GC-MS. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded in d_6 -DMSO with Bruker AM 300L (300 MHz) super-conducting FT NMR. The cobalt content of the complexes was determined³⁵ gravimetrically as anhydrous CoSO_4 , except for the perchlorate species, where the metal was determined³⁵ as the $\text{CoHg}(\text{SCN})_4$ after decomposing the complex with conc. HNO_3 and H_2SO_4 mixture. The nickel content of the species was estimated gravimetrically as nickel dimethyl glyoximate, after decomposing the metal complex with an acid mixture. Copper was estimated iodometrically after decomposing the complex with HNO_3 and HCl mixture followed by boiling with urea³⁵. The halogen content of the complexes was determined as silver halide following the standard procedure. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured on a PAR 155 vibrating-sample magnetometer at IACS, Kolkata. The molar conductance values of the complexes in methanolic solution were obtained with a Systronics model 304 digital conductivity meter and pH measurements with a Systronic system 361 pH meter. The diffused reflectance spectra and the solution spectra of the complexes were recorded on U-3501 spectrophotometer. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer model 883 infrared spectrophotometer. EPR spectra were taken on a Varian E112 spectrometer at RSIC, Kolkata. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded with the cyclic voltammetry model 270/250 Research Electrochemistry Software (version 4.23) at Burdwan University, in methanolic solution of the species ($1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) using

tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (NBu_4ClO_4 , 0.1 M) as supporting electrolyte.

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